

ISic0076

I.Sicily inscription 0076

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

Foot of Mt. Pellegrino

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost, formerly in Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644811

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.09

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Berger, P. 1904. Ex-voto à Tanit découvert en Sicile par le professeur Giacomo de Gregorio. *Comptes rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-*

Lettres. 48: 32-33.

Académie des inscriptions & belles-lettres (France) Commission du Corpus inscriptionum semiticarum, 1900-1968. Répertoire d'épigraphie sémitique. Paris. At (1900) 525

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